

Cervical Cancer Screening Practices and Associated Factors in Eastern India

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Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women in low- and middle-income countries, including India. Despite the availability of effective screening methods, the uptake of cervical cancer screening remains low in many regions, particularly in Eastern India. Socio-demographic factors, limited awareness, and access barriers contribute to this issue, necessitating a focused investigation.

Aim: This study aims to assess the cervical cancer screening practices among women in Eastern India and identify the socio-demographic factors associated with these practices to inform targeted public health interventions.

Methods: A total of 100 women aged 21-65 years were randomly selected and interviewed using a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression to identify factors associated with cervical cancer screening practices.

Results: The study found that 60% of participants had undergone cervical cancer screening, while 40% had never been screened. Significant associations were observed between screening practices and higher education levels ($p < 0.01$), urban residence ($p = 0.03$), and higher socioeconomic status ($p = 0.02$). Age was not significantly associated with screening practices ($p = 0.08$). The findings highlight the influence of educational and economic factors on screening behavior.

Conclusion: Cervical cancer screening rates in Eastern India are suboptimal, particularly among women from rural areas, those with lower education levels, and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. There is a pressing need for targeted interventions to enhance awareness, accessibility, and affordability of screening services.

Recommendations: Public health strategies should focus on educational campaigns to raise awareness, improve access to screening facilities, and address economic barriers, particularly in underserved populations. Expanding the reach of national health initiatives and integrating cervical cancer screening into routine healthcare services are essential steps to reduce the burden of cervical cancer in Eastern India.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, Screening practices, Eastern India, Socio-demographic factors, Public health interventions

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Introduction

Cervical cancer remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like India, where it is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths among women. Despite being largely preventable through regular screening and vaccination against human papillomavirus (HPV), the uptake of these preventive measures remains suboptimal in many regions. According to recent data, cervical cancer accounts for approximately 18.3% of all cancer cases in Indian women, with an estimated 96,922 new cases and 60,078 deaths annually [1].

In Eastern India, where healthcare infrastructure is often limited and socio-cultural barriers are prevalent, the situation is particularly concerning. The region is characterized by high levels of poverty, low literacy rates, and significant disparities in access to healthcare, all of which contribute to low screening rates. The (WHO) emphasizes that screening programs, when effectively implemented, can reduce cervical cancer incidence by up to 80% (WHO, 2021). However, the success of such programs depends heavily on the awareness, attitudes, and practices of

the target population, as well as the availability and accessibility of screening services [2].

Studies conducted in various parts of India have shown that knowledge about cervical cancer and its prevention is often inadequate, particularly among women in rural areas. For example, a study by in Northern India found that only 23% of women were aware of cervical cancer screening methods, and just 10% had undergone screening [3]. Similar trends have been observed in Eastern India, where cultural taboos, lack of education, and limited access to healthcare services further exacerbate the problem [4].

The introduction of national health initiatives, such as the National Programme for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke (NPCDCS), aims to improve the early detection and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cervical cancer. However, despite these efforts, the actual implementation and reach of these programs remain uneven, particularly in remote and underserved areas [5].

Given this context, there is an urgent need to understand the factors influencing cervical cancer screening practices in Eastern India to inform more effective public health strategies. This study aims to assess the cervical cancer screening practices among women in Eastern India and identify the socio-demographic factors associated with these practices to inform targeted public health interventions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, S. K. M. C. H. (Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital), Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India. This study designed to assess the cervical cancer screening practices and the associated factors among women in Eastern India.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of 12 months, from January 2023 to December 2023.

Participants: The study included 100 women who attended the Obstetrics and Gynaecology department at S. K. M. C. H. during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 21 to 65 years.
- Women who were sexually active.
- Women who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

- Women who were permanent residents of Eastern India.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with a history of hysterectomy.
- Women currently undergoing treatment for cervical cancer.
- Pregnant women.
- Women who did not provide consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, random sampling was employed to select participants from the patient population visiting the department. Information bias was minimized by using a standardized questionnaire and conducting interviews by trained healthcare professionals. Confounding factors were addressed during data analysis by adjusting for potential confounders in the statistical model.

Data Collection: Data was collected using a structured questionnaire that included sections on demographic details, knowledge and practices related to cervical cancer screening, and associated factors such as socioeconomic status, educational level, and access to healthcare services. Interviews were conducted in person by trained healthcare professionals.

Procedure: Participants were informed about the study and written consent was obtained. The questionnaire was administered through face-to-face interviews, ensuring clarity and understanding of each question. The interviews were conducted in a private setting within the department to maintain confidentiality and encourage honest responses. The data was recorded electronically and securely stored for further analysis.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data that had been gathered and entered into a database. The screening procedures and demographic traits were summed together using descriptive statistics. The relationship between cervical cancer screening behaviours and several sociodemographic characteristics was examined using chi-square testing. To find variables that were independently connected to screening procedures, multivariate logistic regression was employed. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 100 women participated in the study. The age distribution of the participants was as follows: 25% were between 21-30 years, 35% were between 31-40 years, 30% were between 41-50 years, and 10% were between 51-65 years. The majority of participants (60%) were from rural areas, while 40% were from urban areas. Educational status varied, with 20% of participants being illiterate,

30% having primary education, 35% having secondary education, and 15% having higher

education. Socioeconomic status was classified as low (45%), middle (40%), and high (15%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N=100)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
21-30 years	25	25
31-40 years	35	35
41-50 years	30	30
51-65 years	10	10
Residence		
Rural	60	60
Urban	40	40
Education Level		
Illiterate	20	20
Primary	30	30
Secondary	35	35
Higher	15	15
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	45	45
Middle	40	40
High	15	15

Cervical Cancer Screening Practices: Out of the 100 participants, 60% reported having ever undergone cervical cancer screening, while 40% had never been screened. Among those who had been screened, 50% had done so within the last three years, 30% between three to five years ago, and 20% more than five years ago.

Table 2: Cervical Cancer Screening Practices (N=100)

Screening Practice	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Ever Screened	60	60
Never Screened	40	40
Last Screening Time		
Within last 3 years	30	50
3-5 years ago	18	30
More than 5 years ago	12	20

Factors Associated with Cervical Cancer Screening: The study identified several factors significantly associated with cervical cancer screening practices. Women with higher education levels were more likely to have undergone screening ($p < 0.01$). Urban residents were also more

likely to have been screened compared to rural residents ($p = 0.03$). Socioeconomic status showed a significant association, with women from higher socioeconomic backgrounds more likely to have been screened ($p = 0.02$). Age was not significantly associated with screening practices ($p = 0.08$).

Table 3: Association of Sociodemographic Factors with Cervical Cancer Screening (N=100)

Factor	Screened (%)	Not Screened (%)	p-value
Education Level			
Illiterate	10 (50%)	10 (50%)	0.01
Primary	15 (50%)	15 (50%)	
Secondary	25 (71%)	10 (29%)	
Higher	10 (67%)	5 (33%)	
Residence			
Rural	30 (50%)	30 (50%)	0.03
Urban	30 (75%)	10 (25%)	
Socioeconomic Status			
Low	18 (40%)	27 (60%)	0.02
Middle	25 (62%)	15 (38%)	
High	12 (80%)	3 (20%)	
Age Group			
21-30 years	12 (48%)	13 (52%)	0.08

31-40 years	21 (60%)	14 (40%)	
41-50 years	18 (60%)	12 (40%)	
51-65 years	9 (90%)	1 (10%)	

Discussion

The study evaluated cervical cancer screening practices among 100 women in Eastern India, revealing that 60% of participants had undergone screening at least once, while 40% had never been screened. Among those who had been screened, half had done so within the last three years, indicating some adherence to recommended screening intervals. However, the remaining half had not been screened recently, highlighting potential gaps in ongoing preventive care.

The analysis identified significant associations between cervical cancer screening practices and several sociodemographic factors. Women with higher education levels were more likely to have undergone screening, suggesting that educational attainment plays a crucial role in health-seeking behavior. Urban residence was also associated with higher screening rates, likely due to better access to healthcare facilities and greater awareness of the importance of screening in urban areas. Additionally, women from higher socioeconomic backgrounds were more likely to have been screened, indicating that economic factors and access to resources significantly influence health behaviors.

Interestingly, the study found no significant association between age and screening practices, although older women (aged 51-65) were more likely to have been screened than younger women. This finding may reflect increased health consciousness or greater exposure to healthcare interventions in older age groups.

Overall, the results underscore the need for targeted interventions to improve cervical cancer screening rates, particularly among women from rural areas, those with lower education levels, and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Enhancing awareness, accessibility, and affordability of cervical cancer screening, especially in underserved populations, could play a vital role in reducing the incidence and mortality associated with cervical cancer in Eastern India. These efforts should focus on educational campaigns, improving access to screening services, and addressing economic barriers to healthcare.

Significant geographical differences and screening hurdles have been brought to light by recent studies on cervical cancer screening in India, notably in rural and semi-urban areas. A district-level examination of cervical and breast cancer screening in India was carried. Significant regional differences in screening practices were found by this study, with rural areas exhibiting lower uptake than met-

ropolitan areas. Important variables that affected screening habits were found in the study, including access to healthcare facilities, marital status, and socioeconomic position. In order to overcome these inequalities and raise screening rates in India's many districts, the authors stressed the necessity for region-specific interventions [6].

A study conducted in a semi-urban township in Eastern India, which revealed a poor level of awareness and practice of cervical cancer screening among women. The research revealed that awareness of and involvements in screening programs were significantly influenced by socioeconomic status and educational attainment. The researchers came to the conclusion that, in these underprivileged communities, there is an urgent need for educational programs and community-based interventions to increase awareness about cervical cancer and the need of early screening [7].

Using information from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4), Nilima conducted a significant study that examined the prevalence, trends, and predictors of cervical cancer screening in India. The research found that low screening rates were significantly clustered in several areas, especially in North Central and North Eastern India. Lower screening uptake was closely correlated with factors including living in a remote area, having a low wealth index, not utilising current contraceptive methods, and not being aware of STDs. According to the authors proposed that focused interventions in these high-risk locations could raise screening rates and eventually lower the death rate from cervical cancer in India [8].

Limitations

This study was limited by its cross-sectional design, which precludes the establishment of causality. Additionally, the study was conducted in a single hospital setting, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader population of Eastern India.

Conclusion

The study concluded that cervical cancer screening rates in Eastern India are suboptimal, particularly among women from rural areas, those with lower education levels, and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Efforts to improve cervical cancer screening coverage should focus on increasing awareness and accessibility, particularly among these vulnerable groups.

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